

Physico-chemical Properties of some Indian Vermiculites

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Physico-chemical properties of some of the Indian vermiculites have been studied by X-ray, D. T. A., electrochemical, and viscometric methods.

Characterisation of vermiculites by physical methods, such as X-ray, differential thermal analyses^{1,2,3}, and chemical methods like electrochemical and viscometric methods^{4,6} are well known. Study of this 2:1-layer clay mineral has some special interest as it possesses the following characteristics: (i) It holds lattice expanding capacity; (ii) it exhibits high base-exchange properties; (iii) H-clay behaves like a tribasic acid; (iv) it exhibits a strong reflection at $14\text{ \AA}$ in X-ray diffraction diagrams, particularly when Mg-saturated; (v) the lattice contracts on (a) gradual heating to higher temperatures and (b) potash saturation.

The present investigation is intended for characterisation of some of Indian vermiculites and includes physical methods like X-ray, D.T.A., electrochemical, and viscometric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Clay fractions of particle size less than $2\ \mu$ were extracted from wet ground samples by the usual process of dispersion with dilute KOH solution and sedimentation for 8 hr.⁶, converted into H-clay by leaching with 0.02N-HCl, made free of organic matter, and finally electro dialysed. The b.e.c. values of H-clays were determined by the method of Ganguli⁵; the potentiometric and conductometric titrations were done as well as viscosity changes were noted with gradual neutralisation of H-clay with KOH after equilibrating for 24 hr.⁶ The chemical analysis of H-clays (on oven-dry basis) and X-ray and D.T.A. measurements were carried out by the usual procedures^{5,7}.

The vermiculites under investigation were collected through the courtesy of Petrologist, G.S.I., from Hazaribagh district (Bihar), Andhra State (South), Sitarampuram (a place northern part of Andhra State), and Ajmer (Rajasthan).

1. Grim, "Clay Mineralogy", McGraw Hill Book Co., Inc., 1953.
2. Marshall, "The Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals", Academic Press Inc., 1949.
3. Walker, "X-Ray Identification & Crystal Structure of Clay Minerals", Mineralogical Society, London, p. 204, 1951.
4. Barshad, *Am. Mineralogist*, 1948, **33**, 655.
5. Adhikari and Ray, *Science & Culture*, 1957, **23**, 258.
6. Adhikari, *J. Ind. Soil Sci.*, 1957, **5**, 199.
7. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1955.

Experimental results are recorded in Tables I-V.

TABLE I

Chemical analysis.

(No. 1 on air-dry basis and the rest on the oven-dry basis).

Sl. No.	Source.	%SiO ₂ .	%Al ₂ O ₃ .	%FeO.	%Fe ₂ O ₃ .	%MgO.	%Na ₂ O.	%K ₂ O.	%Loss on ignition	Molar ratio $\left(\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}\right)_2$
1	Hazaribagh (natural sample)	32.21	16.67	Not determined	8.60	21.26	0.06	0.11	21.55	3.27
2	Hazaribagh (H-clay)	35.08	17.05	1.43	16.79	15.70	0.50	6.02	5.58	3.25
3	Andhra (H-clay) South	37.63	18.26	2.60	8.77	12.35	0.43	1.95	16.35	2.49
4	Sitarampuram (H-clay)	31.68	18.97	1.43	10.07	14.56	0.12	5.76	9.36	2.83
5	Ajmer (H-clay) Rajasthan	37.88	19.88	12.98	11.62	15.97	0.20	5.95	4.83	3.23

The natural sample as well as the H-clay does not seem to contain any calcium. The general formula of vermiculites is $(\text{OH})_4(\text{MgCa})_x(\text{Si}_{8-x}\text{Al}_x)(\text{Mg, Fe})_6\text{O}_{20}\cdot y\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with $x=1-1.4$, $y=8$. The charge distributions in the lattices (as calculated by the method of Marshall⁸) of H-clays investigated are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Charge distribution and interlayer cations in vermiculites (unit cell of 24 oxygen atoms).

Source.	Tetrahedral charge.	Octahedral charge.	Interlayer cations (atoms).
Hazaribagh (H-clay)	-2.7528	+1.2224	K : 1.1685 Na: 0.1601 H : 0.2023
Andhra (H-clay)	-2.2357	+0.5608	K : 0.3845 Na: 0.1269 H : 1.1685
Sitarampuram(H-clay)	-3.1182	+1.6237	K ; 1.1445 Na: 0.0352 H : 0.2796
Ajmer (H-clay)	-2.4651	+0.4910	K : 1.1010 Na: 0.0526 H : 0.2704

The charge deficiency in the lattice of original vermiculite sample from Hazaribagh is -2.7614 in the tetrahedral layer and is wholly balanced by Mg and to a very little extent by Na and K. This sample during isolation of clay becomes saturated with K⁺ ions and partly with H⁺ ions during H-clay formation.

TABLE III

Electrochemical properties.

Samples.	%Clay content.	B.E.C.	pH.	Inflection points.		Ratio of bases.
				Conductance.	KOH.	
Hazariabagh	2.106	23.20	7.2	23×10^{-6} mho	13.5 m.e.	1.77
			9.1	$69 \times$	24.0	
Andhra (South)	0.436	129.00	8.0	$12 \times$	68.0	1.64
			9.4	$13 \times$	112.0	
Sitarampuram	2.600	30.26	7.2	$40 \times$	28.0	1.57
			9.0	$78 \times$	44.0	
Ajmer	1.636	30.80	7.2	$24 \times$	22.0	1.60
			9.0	$65 \times$	35.0	

The H-clays from Hazariabagh, Sitarampuram and Ajmer have low b.e.c. values. This has also been observed by the Adhikari and Ray⁵ in the case of Malavangatta vermiculite. This may partly be due to the fact that as a result of charge deficit in the Si-layer, the lattice of H-clays is negatively charged and the balancing interlayer cation is mainly K⁺. Another reason for low b.e.c. may be due to presence of impurities like sesquioxides, etc.

The titration curve of H-vermiculite from Hazariabagh with KOH shows one inflection at 7.2 pH, conductance equivalence at 23×10^{-6} mho (13.50 m.e. of KOH) with buffering in the region of pH 5.4-6.0 (3-7 m.e. of KOH). The curve (not shown) also shows another inflection at pH 9.1, 60×10^{-6} mho (24 m.e. KOH). The ratio of bases at the inflection points is 1.77. Titrations in the alkaline range over pH 10 were not done.

The titration curve of H-clay from Andhra shows one inflection at pH 8.0, conductance equivalence at $\times 10^{-6}$ mho (68 m.e. KOH); there is another inflection at pH 9.4., conductance equivalence 13×10^{-6} at 112 m.e. KOH. The ratio of bases corresponding to the inflection points is 1.64.

The titration curve of H-clay from Sitarampuram shows a sharp inflection at pH 7.2 (28. m.e. KOH), conductance equivalence at 40×10^{-6} mho with buffering in the region pH 5.6-6.4. There is another inflection at 9.0 pH, conductance equivalence at 78 m.e. of KOH. The ratio of bases corresponding to these inflections is 1.57°.

The titration curve of H-clay from Ajmer, shows one inflection at pH 7.2, conductance equivalence at 24×10^{-6} mho (22 m.e. KOH) and also another inflection at pH 9.0, conductance equivalence at 65×10^{-6} mho (36 m.e. KOH). The ratio of bases corresponding to these inflection points is 1.6.

Viscous Properties.—Apart from a slight initial decrease, the viscosity of 0.5% suspensions of H-vermiculites does not appear to change on the addition of increasing amounts of KOH.

The original sample from Hazariabagh shows the basal reflection at 14.04 Å, whereas H-clay contracts to 10.02 Å. This may be partly due to K-saturation during isolation of clay⁶ and partly to heat treatment. This fact has been corroborated with the results of chemical

6. Harvard *et al.*, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1961, 25, 535,

analysis (Table I). Mg-saturation of this H-clay does not provide the basal spacing at $14\text{\AA}$. H-clay from Sitarampuram partly collapses to a spacing between 12.12 and $9.73\text{\AA}$. Ajmer sample is not pure vermiculite and exhibits the standard diffraction data of biotite (cf. spacings at 9.67 , 3.33 , 2.61 , $2.42\text{\AA}$ etc.)

TABLE IV

Lattice spacings and estimated intensities in powder diagrams of vermiculites.

Original sample.		H a z a r i b a g h.			A n d h r a (South).		S i t a r a m p u r a m.		A j m e r, original sample.		
<i>d.</i>	<i>I.</i>	<i>d.</i>	<i>I.</i>	<i>d.</i>	<i>I.</i>	<i>d.</i>	<i>I.</i>	<i>d.</i>	<i>I.</i>	<i>d.</i>	<i>I.</i>
14.04	vs	10.02	m(d)	10.01	ms	14.04	w	12.12	w	9.67	vs
7.17	vw							9.73	diffuse		
4.56	ms	4.51	w	4.56	w	4.56	w	4.57	w	4.63	vw
		4.19	w	4.50	vw	4.24	vw	5.14	vw		
3.56	ms	3.91	w	3.66	ms						
		3.67	w	3.34	ms	3.30	ms	3.33	w	3.33	ms
2.63	ms	3.37	ms	3.16	w			3.13	vw		
2.63	ms	3.10	w	2.90	vw						
2.50	ms	2.90	w	2.60	vs	2.50	w	2.61	vs	2.61	vs
2.38	vs	2.61	vs	2.39	vs	2.39	ms	2.39	vw	2.42	ms
		2.50	vw	2.14	ms			2.29	vw	2.26	vw
1.52	vs	2.40	ms	2.03	w			2.15	ms	2.17	w
		2.26	w	1.88	vw			1.99	vw	1.97	w
		2.15	ms	1.65	ms			1.65	w	1.89	vw
		2.02	w	1.52		1.51	ms	1.52	vs	1.65	w
		1.65	w	1.35	vw			1.34	vw	1.43	ms
		1.53	vs	1.31	w			1.32	w	1.36	vw
		1.47	vw							1.32	vw
		1.36	w								
		1.32	w								
		1.28	w								
		1.23	w								
		1.17	w								

X-Ray Data.—For want of special type camera, the first order spacings of glycerol-saturated vermiculite around 24 KX could not be recorded. During later studies it was found that on thallos salt treatment of these vermiculites, the 14 KX lines almost diminished in intensity. This indicates the conformity with earlier observation that the samples are vermiculites⁹. The basal spacing of less than 14 KX has also been reported by Adhikari and Ray³.

D. T. A.—The natural sample from Hazaribagh provided two endothermic peaks. One sharp peak at 135° and a second one at $535-54^\circ$, but in H-clay the first peak shifts to $140-50^\circ$ and the second one at 560° . This is also the case with Sitarampuram. H-vermiculite from Andhra shows two peaks, one at 135° and another at $545-50^\circ$. The H-vermiculite of Ajmer provides two peaks, one at $175-80^\circ$ and another at 545° .

9. Ganguli, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1417.

10. Kittrick, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1961, 5, 470.

TABLE V

		Endothermic peaks.	
Hazaribagh	(Original sample)	135°	535-45°
Hazaribagh	H-Clay	140-50°	560°
Andhra (South)	"	135°	545-50°
Sitarampuram	"	140-50°	560°
Ajmer	"	175-80°	545°

The absence of high temperature exothermic, followed by an endothermic, peak may be due to small particle size and weak crystallinity⁶.

Depending on the methods of 'isolation of clays', lattice contraction takes place from 14 Å basal spacing to 10 Å. Expansion of lattice will not occur even after Mg-saturation with some of these clays. The size of the particles exerts some influence on the base exchange capacity and X-ray spacings. More useful results on size and shape of the particles are likely to be revealed by the electron microscope. This case will be pursued later on. Electrochemical and viscometric data are not sufficient to characterise them to be vermiculite and hence to be supplemented with X-ray and D.T.A. data.

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